

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Report for Milestones

Document info

Title	Create editorial guidelines and template for each component of the training life cycle to follow for content consistency in each page
Deliverable/Milestone Number	M3.2
Responsible Participant	Alexander Botzki
WP Number	WP3
Dissemination level (PU/ RE/ CO / or NA)	PU

*For types of deliverables please see [Guidelines for ELIXIR Commissioned Services](#)

Version history

Version	Revised by	Date	Comment
0.1	draft	14/11/2025	
1.0.0	Alexander Botzki	23/12/2024	
1.0.1	SPLASH editorial board members: Alexander Botzki Alexia Cardona Elin Kronander Geert Van Geest Bruna Piereck	29/01/2025	
1.0.2		XX/01/2025	
	Content Check by WP1	07/02/2025	ok'ed during ExCo call
	Admin Check by Hub (CoS Portfolio Manager)		

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

ETrP	ELIXIR Training Platform
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Executive Summary

Milestone M3.2 of the ELIXIR SPLASH project focuses on creating editorial guidelines and templates for each component of the training life cycle. This ensures content consistency across all pages of the SPLASH platform.

The primary objective is to enhance the accessibility and long-term impact of ELIXIR Training Platform (ETrP) resources by providing a unified, consistent framework for content creation. The problem addressed is the current dispersion of training resources across various channels, making it difficult to maintain a comprehensive and consistent training approach.

The ELIXIR SPLASH project aims to centralize and showcase the diverse training resources developed by ETrP. By creating a "one-stop-shop" digital platform, SPLASH seeks to raise awareness and recognition of training efforts and ensure sustainable, high-quality training practices.

Alternatives considered included maintaining the status quo of dispersed resources or developing separate guidelines for each training component without a unified template. These alternatives were deemed less effective in achieving content consistency and long-term sustainability.

The milestone was successfully achieved following initial discussions at the Biohackathon 2023. Templates for each stage of the training life cycle and SPLASH resources were defined, and editorial guidelines were based on the ELIXIR RDMkit. These guidelines have been reviewed and are now accessible via the SPLASH website. Future refinements will be made by the newly formed editorial board to adapt to evolving needs.

By standardizing content creation, the SPLASH project ensures that training resources are not only accessible but also adhere to the highest educational standards, fostering sustainable and impactful training programs in the life sciences.

Outcomes and Impacts of the milestone

Milestone M3.2 Create editorial guidelines and template for each component of the training life cycle to follow for content consistency in each page is part of the SPLASH project. The output of this milestone was finalised and the editorial guidelines and the template for the component of the life cycle are now displayed on the SPLASH website.

Figure 1: The Training Life Cycle¹

This milestone was achieved after initial discussions during the Biohackathon 2023 where templates of the stage of the training life cycle as well as the [SPLASH resources](#) have been defined. For the editorial guidelines, we based ourselves on the initial editorial guidelines of the ELIXIR RDMkit as an excellent starting point. These guidelines have been reviewed during the process of creating the content of the initial release of SPLASH. They are now accessible in sub-menus via the [Contribute](#) menu of SPLASH.

We anticipate that the editorial guidelines will be finetuned in subsequent meetings of the [newly composed editorial board](#) of SPLASH and adapted in case more templates of SPLASH content like e.g. a trainer template or a national resource template will be created in the next 2 years of the ELIXIR Training programme.

¹ <https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-Training-SPLASH/>